

CLIMATE SMART ACTIONS FOR LIVESTOCK FARMS

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WHAT IS IT?

Climate Smart Actions (CSA), applied to livestock, refers to different farming management practices on livestock farms. CSA focus on the mitigation and adaptation to climate change of different livestock farm types¹. And these practices are based on data collected from farmers and appropriate calculations. Nowadays, there is an increasing interest on the reintegration of livestock and crops which can provide a significant development of circular economy and contribute to sustainable growth². This can be managed through the recycling of materials and resources, the minimization of waste, and a reduction in external inputs, with potential biodiversity, environmental and soil health benefits.

WHAT ARE THE BENEFITS?

- Increase livestock farm productivity and incomes.
- Adapt and build resilience to climate change.
- Reduce or remove livestock farm contribution to greenhouse gas emission, where possible.

Livestock dietary improvement and management

Feed quality and nutrition affect animal's productivity and health and can influence GHG emissions by animals. Feed and nutrition can be managed through changes on animal diets, better grassland management or changes on pasture species³.

By building an appropriate diet, we could manage enteric CH₄ emissions, N excretion and animal production, as well as soil C sequestration and N₂O emissions for grazed crops and/or crop residues used for feed. In this context, the use in animal diets of (i) new species mixtures containing tannins and high sugar contents, (ii) seed amendments (seaweed, others) and (iii) the share of grasslands/croplands (legume forage, corn, silage, grazing, etc.), needs to be tested.

Crop residue grazing can be a viable component of integrated crop-livestock system to add circularity sustaining overall agricultural production⁴. It is important to examine the benefits, synergies and trade-offs that grazing crop residues may provide using conventional grazing in combination with partial grazing on cropland residues.

Manure and amendment management

Animal excreta represents about a quarter of agricultural GHG emissions and manure management is an important practice to mitigate these emissions inputs^{5,6}. Reintroduction of crops and livestock provide the potential for lowering CH₄ and nitrous oxide emissions from livestock excreta and reducing effluent discharges, with manure substituting for most synthetic fertilizer inputs. Moreover, manure management may reduce nutrient losses from livestock production systems and air and water pollution.

Changes of livestock diet may impact GHG emissions of the manure. It should be determined how crops and livestock can be integrated into new systems and their optimum configuration for dietary changes related to land use and management practices. The effects of these practices on manure management needs to be measured to evaluate GHG emission sources for the whole farm system.

Regarding manure management, the conversion of manure via anaerobic digestion (e.g., in a biogas plant) could be a partially sustainable solution since it produces two by-products (solid and liquid digestates), which have the potential to be used as fertilizers and/or soil amendments⁷. However, the effectiveness of these digestates as organic amendments and fertilizers is still under debate. On the other hand, biochar is a product that provide carbon-rich materials. Biochar can sequester carbon in soils and improve soil properties and combined with mineral fertilizers and digestates could overcome nutrient deficiencies⁸. Using biochar with manures is an alternative option rather than applying them separately to the soil. Anyway, the environmental effects of biogas generation, the use of different amendments to replace synthetic fertilizer and the use of biochar needs to be assess.

Crop and soil management choices

Of great interest is to evaluate the GHG balance of integrated crop-livestock

systems to elucidate the optimum configuration of land uses and management/grazing practices. Different livestock farm types can be assessed through the interaction with farmers and appropriated calculations which could bring us information of the effectiveness, reliability and practical applicability of the management selected.

Moreover, the study of soil microbiology and soil laboratory incubations can also be used to evaluate de capacity for soil carbon sequestration and methane oxidation of the different managements. Soil types and additives (e.g. manure, compost, biochar...) can be study in the laboratory to better understand the mechanisms underlying C storage capacity and methanotrophy activity.

Specifically, to select the optimum configuration of land uses and management practices some experimental farming practices can be study:

- Improved grassland management: forage diversification, overseeding legume-rich pastures, rotational grazing.
- Conversion of arable land to grassland.
- Better integration of cropland with livestock: the use of fodder crops, grazing cover crops, set-aside fallows and crop residues.
- Agroforestry combinations: forest grazing (reduction of wildfire risk), creation of woody pastures by the planting of trees on grasslands, woody forage banks and palatable hedgerows.
- The potential for valorisation of woody crops and biochar derived from various feedstocks and pruning offcuts as a fertilizer/feed and disease suppressor, and the use of wood chips as a soil conditioner.

Systems-based decision support tools for identifying the best options for farmers

Farm modelling can identify a combination of land uses and management scenarios to optimise circularity and reduce GHG emissions. Through modelling we can

analyse the benefits, limitations, and trade-offs of the reintegration of livestock with cropping systems either alone or in combination with agroforestry or afforestation at a farm scale.

CHALLENGES

The reintegration of crops and livestock could provide benefits, but this comes with significant challenges. Changes on animal's diet can improve nutrient uptake, increase animal productivity and fertility, and thus lower emissions per unit of product. But care needs to be taken, that those emissions from off farm production of supplementary feeds and/or processing do not outweigh any on-farm reductions. The

application of organic amendments could increase leaching and the necessity to store large amounts of organic manures, which may further increase GHG emissions and environmental pollution. Additional complications could arise due to competition between food and animal feed and/or the use of land for bioenergy crops. Another key issue is the economic consequences of reintroducing livestock with cropping systems. Whilst mixed farming systems were previously common and economically viable, new developments require them to be matched with current production and market conditions and suitable value chains and business models to ensure their long-term viability and sustainability.

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For more detailed information about the practice implemented, benefits and data, please refer to: <https://relive-era.net/>